

Supplementary Figure Legends

Fig. S1 Supporting for Fig1. A, GO cellular component (CC) analysis of the DEGs. B, GO molecular function (MF) analysis of the DEGs. C, GO biological process (BP) analysis of the DEGs. D, The KEGG pathway analysis.

Fig. S2 Supporting for Fig2. A, The bubble plot showing specific expressed genes of different cell types. B, The UMAP plots show the distribution of different cell types in different samples.

Fig. S3 Supporting for Fig3. A, GO cellular component (CC) analysis of the DEGs. B, GO molecular function (MF) analysis of the DEGs. C, GO biological process (BP) analysis of the DEGs. D, The KEGG pathway analysis.

A

B

Fig. S4 Supporting for Fig4. A, Network diagram showing cellular communication between fibroblast and other different cell types. B, The distribution of four key communication networks in OC, including CD99, TNF, GRN and COLLAGEN signaling pathway.

A

■	hsa04510	KEGG Pathway	Focal adhesion
■	hsa04512	KEGG Pathway	ECM-receptor interaction
■	WP306	WikiPathways	Focal adhesion
■	WP2911	WikiPathways	miRNA targets in ECM and membrane receptors
■	R-HSA-3000171	Reactome Gene Sets	Non-integrin membrane-ECM interactions
■	M53	Canonical Pathways	PID INTEGRIN3 PATHWAY
■	GO:0035987	GO Biological Processes	endodermal cell differentiation
■	GO:0001568	GO Biological Processes	blood vessel development
■	M174	Canonical Pathways	PID UPA UPAR PATHWAY
■	M3008	Canonical Pathways	NABA ECM GLYCOPROTEINS
■	GO:0001503	GO Biological Processes	ossification
■	GO:0045765	GO Biological Processes	regulation of angiogenesis
■	GO:0002009	GO Biological Processes	morphogenesis of an epithelium

Fig.

S5 Supporting for Fig6. A, The function enrichment network of 15 key genes.